

Impact of IFRS 10 Adoption on Profitability of Listed Deposit Money Banks (LDMBs) In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) 10 is an amendment of International Accounting Standard (IAS) 27 that deals with Consolidated Financial Statements to account for subsidiaries, in order to institute a unitary control model that can be applicable throughout the organization. The amendment requires the implementers of IFRS 10 to emphasize a great judgement in determining if the entities are being controlled to warrant consolidation by the parent firm. This is because the procedures of consolidation for IFRS 10 do not change but only concerned with the option of whether an entity should be consolidated based on its new definition of control or not. This study therefore examined the impact of IFRS 10 adoption on the profitability of Listed Deposit Money Banks (LDMBs) in Nigeria with a view to finding out if there are variations in the performance of LDMBs pre- and post-consolidation era. The study used ex-post facto research design and had a population of 14 LDMBs appearing in the Fact-Book of the NSE as at 31st December 2020. Secondary source of data was used in gathering data from Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) Fact-Book as well as Annual Reports and Accounts of six (6) sampled banks. The sample size was arrived at through purposive/judgmental sampling technique based on a filter that the bank must not have changed its original name over the period of the study. The independent variables examined included consolidated earnings on assets, consolidated earnings on equity, consolidated earnings per share and consolidated dividend per share. The technique of data analysis adopted by the study was independent t-test and the findings indicated that, adoption of IFRS 10 had negative and significant impact on consolidated earnings on assets, but on the contrary, it had positive and significant impact on earnings per share and dividend per share. Findings also revealed positive but insignificant impact on return on equity of LDMBs in Nigeria over the period, it was therefore recommended that LDMBs in Nigeria should continue to adopt IFRS 10 to enhance a better financial performance of consolidated return on equity, earnings per share as well as dividend per share of LDMBs in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Dividend per Share, Earnings per share, Earnings on Assets, Earnings on equity, IFRS 10 adoption

1.0 INTRODUCTION

As a result of the increase in the exigencies of business organizations and the global village nature of capital markets of the modern time, it became compulsory for local/foreign investors, firms, regulators, audit firms and other interested parties to adopt a common standard in financial reporting. This need, gave rise to globally accepted accounting standards that became the foundation for International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). Accounting data has generally been regarded as the business language for measuring performance and subsequent reporting to stakeholders through a common language. The adoption of IFRS by countries has made this statement a reality because business language in figures can be spoken, accepted and understood by various investors and stakeholders across the globe (Adejor & Hasnah, 2014). One of the expectations from the adoption of IFRS was that it would reduce earnings variability and reduce information asymmetry to enhance communication and lower agency costs among stakeholders in both manufacturing and service rendering firms such as banks (Tanko, 2012). As a result of these expectations, Nigeria adopted International Financial Reporting Standard as a standard reporting tool among its business organizations for regulating the quality of financial reports being prepared. In Nigeria, the banking industry is presently the most regulated sector because of the good corporate governance codes that have been put in place by Central Bank of Nigeria, in addition to IFRS adoption of various standards in reporting such as treatment of impairment, consolidation of financial statements, financial instruments classification, income recognition amongst others (Ekwe, Abaa, Okrolor & Ashibeti 2020). IFRS 10 which is part of IFRS is an amendment of International Accounting Standard (IAS) 27 that deals with Consolidated Financial Statements to account for subsidiaries in order to institute a unitary control model that can be applicable throughout the organization. Yahaya

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and Ademola (2011), opined that the amendment requires the implementers of IFRS 10 to emphasize a great judgement in determining if the entities are being controlled to warrant consolidation by the parent firm. This is because the procedures of consolidation for IFRS 10 do not change but only concerned with the option of whether an entity should be consolidated based on its new definition of control or not (PKF, 2018). It is believed therefore that as a consequence of the adoption of IFRS 10 which gives a guide on entities to be consolidated by parent firms, the profitability of listed deposit money banks (LDMBs) such as earnings on assets, earnings on equity, earnings for every share held and dividend for every share held may have been affected. It is against this background that the researchers are investigating the impact of IFRS 10 adoption on consolidated financial accounts of LDMBs in Nigeria. International Accounting Standard-IAS 27 which deals with the construction of consolidated financial accounts for firms usually include or exclude particular entities from its consolidated financial statements (Hsu, Dhu & Cheng, 2012). As part of IAS 27, for a parent company to exercise control over the subsidiary, it must have the "power to govern" (majority share-holding) and receive "benefits" (positive returns) from the subsidiary as necessary conditions for consolidation. Consequently, this led to the introduction of IFRS10 which focuses on Consolidated Financial accounts in replacement of IAS 27. With the introduction of IFRS 10 which uses principle-based in the definition of control, organizations are now limited in their ability to omit loss making entities from consolidated financial reports because they are now also required to include in their consolidation, other entities from which they get both positive and negative earnings and non-majority shareholding entities. Since after introduction of IFRS 10, there had been few studies carried out to compare study of pre and post IFRS 10 adoption in Nigeria. For example, Ekwe, Abaa, Okrolor and Ashibeti (2020) carried out investigation on the impact of IFRS on financial accounts of banks wherein they used earnings on assets, earnings on equity and earnings for every share held as variables of profitability while ANOVA was used as a tool of analysis among banks. However, this particular study used earnings on assets, earnings on equity, earnings for every share held and dividend for every share held as proxies of profitability while independent T-test served as a tool of analysis to compare analysis of pre and post IFRS 10 and these, presented gaps that were filled by this study. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to examine the impact of IFRS 10 adoption on profitability of LDMBs in Nigeria. This study will be beneficial to regulators like Security and Exchange Commission-SEC, Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria-FRCN and investors by providing relevant literatures. The scope of study covers the period, 2003-2020.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

Conceptual reviews

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) produced the IFRS because they offer broad principles for specific treatments of entries in the relevant books, IFRS are generally regarded as a principle-based set of standards. Furthermore, Alistair (2010) described IFRS as an embodiment of accounting pronouncements being issued by IASB to assist financial accounts preparers worldwide in producing transparent and comparable high-quality financial data. Fasoranti, Adelakun, and Joshua (2014) defined IFRS as a set of guidelines that enhance financial disclosure. As a result of these factors, the IFRS are a solid, principle-based, worldwide collection of accounting standards with precise disclosure requirements that are valuable to a variety of users for making decisions. In Nigeria, Federal Government formally proclaimed IFRS adoption on September 2, 2010, along with the scheme to be followed for its implementation, making the country one of the first countries in the world to do so. The adoption of IFRS in Nigeria was done in three phases, phase one required that listed and important public interest businesses should prepare and submit audited financial statements in accordance with applicable IFRS by 31st December 2012. In addition, phase two of IFRS adoption in Nigeria which focused on public interest firms required conformity with the IFRS format by 31st December, 2013. The third and last phase focused on all Small and Medium Businesses (NASB,2010).

Accounting standards are the laws and regulations, opinions, interpretations, and concepts that govern corporations in compiling their financial reports, according to Akabom-Itam (2013). They are information systems that create financial and monetized data for economic decision-making. Accounting standards are useful in financial reporting because they provide recommendations recording and analyzing financial statements so that the information can be meaningful and relevant to the users for communicating their financial performance to various stakeholders (Ding, Hope, Jeanjean & Stolowy, 2007).

In addition, Ahmed (2011) defined profitability as the differential in the cost of supplying goods or services and the revenue accruing from such activities (sales). Profitability is significant because profit maximization is usually thought to be the main goal of commercial organizations in economics. It is also thought that, in addition to profit maximization, an organization needs to make money in order to exist, grow, and maintain its activities. According to DwiPrastowo (2008), earnings or return on assets (ROA) measures the type of profitability that showcases a firm's ability to profit from its assets. Therefore, profit is a ratio that gauges the amount of investments returns made by a firm using all of its capital (assets). Return on equity is another profitability metric that analyzes a firm's financial performance and is stated as a proportion of profit after taxes to total equity. It is normally

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computed before common shareholders get their dividends and after preference stockholders get their dividends and lenders get their interest (Epstein, 2009).

Earnings per share (EPS) is a measure of a firm's profitability that is distributed to each common stockholder, and it is typical for companies to publish EPS that have been adjusted for non-recurring items, prospective share dilution, and other factors (Ibiamke & Ateboh-Briggs, 2014). Furthermore, Dividend for every share held (DPS) is the sum of dividend declared by firms for distribution to ordinary shareholders, and a firm's DPS is frequently calculated using the most recent year dividend payment, and it is also used in the determination of dividend yield for that year.

The amount a firm pays out in dividends is instantly translated into income for shareholders and this makes DPS one of the most useful and straightforward number an investor can use to calculate dividend payments from their investments over time (Adejoh, & Hasnah, 2014).

Theoretical Review

According to institutional theory, organizations must follow rules, regulations, and belief systems that govern the milieu in which they function in order to survive. In the context of IFRS adoption initiatives parlance, an institutionalization is defined as a functional social process in which a country sets aside its domestic accounting standards which had been in use over time with a view to adopting international accounting standard for convergence and harmonization so as to maintain uniform reports. According to Wahyunic (2012), this is typically done on economic grounds with the hopes of bringing economic benefits to the country, such as lower capital costs or a quantum leap in foreign direct investment to the country's capital market.

Empirical Review

Several empirical reviews had been conducted on the impact of IFRS adoption both in Nigeria and in diaspora, for example, Okoye and Akenbor (2014) used a descriptive research design of stock price and shares movement over two years to investigate the influence of IFRS usage on stock movements in the Nigeria stock market. The study used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 7.0 in calculating the variance, standard deviation, and mean, and it was discovered that there was an improvement in the credibility of financial statements preparation after the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria and provided a foundation for corporate entities' strength in the capital market. In a different scenario, Trabelis and Trabelis (2014) also carried out a study on the value relevance of accounting data for banks in Dubai over 2008 to 2013, based on Feltham and Ohlson (1993) return and price models (1995). From January 2008 to March 2014, a sample of 12 banks listed in Dubai was employed, comprising 214 firm-quarterly observations. Because earnings had a positive and significant effect on stock prices and returns, the study's findings indicated that accounting information is linked to market value.

Furthermore, Umobong and Akani (2015) conducted a study on the differences in the quality of accounting data by listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria which took a look at pre- and post-adoption of the IFRS over a five-year period, and this was analyzed using the Multiple regression technique of analysis. The study made use of profits management, value relevance, and prompt loss recognition as independent variables, and it indicated a worrisome outcome in accounting quality across the study period. It was also discovered that in the post-IFRS period, returns and book value of equity are less value relevant, and prompt loss recognition is also less than in the pre-IFRS period. Besides, Abata (2015) conducted a study using comparative-degree index approach for analysis and t-test approach in testing for significant difference. The research used the 14 LDMBs as sample size of the study, while data were gathered using secondary method of data collection. The implementation of IFRS has had a favorable and considerable influence on financial reporting in Nigerian LDMBs, according to the findings. Yahaya, Yusuf, and Dania (2015) used an *ex-post facto* study approach to assess the impact of the IFRS on the financial accounts of LDMBs in Nigeria from 2004 to 2008 and 2009 to 2013. The secondary data were analyzed using logistic regression using a dummy variable as dependent variable and growth, profitability, size leverage, liquidity, age, and investment as the independent variables. The findings indicated that adoption of IFRS had a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of Nigeria's LDMBs, because key financial performance indicators such as profitability and growth were higher under IFRS.

Umobong (2015) also made use of listed food and beverage manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria to evaluate and assess the effect of IFRS adoption on performance of firms with a focus on earnings for every share held, price earnings ratio, and dividend yield as independent variables in the study, and data were collected and analyzed before and after the implementation of the IFRS. To determine the impact of pre- and post-IFRS adoption on firms' market performance, the independent T test was utilized as a data analysis approach. The study's findings revealed that there are no significant differences in market performance between pre- and post-IFRS eras, implying a weak link between IFRS adoption and market performance.

Ironkwe (2016) used secondary data and the t-statistics technique to evaluate IFRS and corporate performance of listed enterprises in Nigeria. The findings disclosed a positive nexus between IFRSs and performance of Nigerian listed companies. Eneje, Obidike, and Chukwujekwu (2016) looked into the impact of adopting IFRS on loan loss provisioning for Nigerian LDMBs, over a

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period of 2005 to 2015. Secondary data were gathered from the annual financial data of LDMBs and descriptive statistics and the ordinary least square multiple regression technique was used in the analysis. It was discovered that IAS 39's requirement of recognizing only incurred losses has the potential of reducing income smoothing, which enhances quality of earnings but hampers recognition of future predicted losses, which in turn affected quality of asset.

Similarly, Akinleye (2016) investigated the relationship between IFRS adoption and LDMB performance in Nigeria using ratio analysis. Over the years 2009 to 2014, ten financial institutions (banks) were selected randomly for analysis and secondary data obtained from the annual financial reports and used a panel data pooled OLS technique. The study's findings revealed that adoption of IFRS has a beneficial even though, minor impact on the performance of LDMBs in Nigeria. Uzodimma and Okpala (2017) carried out a study in Nigeria on the influence of IFRS on the performance of LDMBs, the study utilized secondary data from annual financial accounts of five LDMBs from 2009 to 2016, and analyzing the data using the Wilcoxon model. It was discovered that implementation of IFRS has an ample favorable effect on the profitability of Nigerian deposit money institutions.

Eriki, Modebe, Okoye, and Erin (2017) also used secondary data from 2009 to 2015 to conduct a study on the impact of IFRS on key financial ratios of 11 LDMBs in Nigeria. Profitability ratios, short-term solvency ratios, long-term solvency ratios, and investment ratios were all analyzed using the Mann Whitney U-Test method. According to the findings, the IFRS(IFRS) had a favorable and significant impact on the performance of LDMBs in Nigeria.

"Does IFRS(IFRS) Impact on Profitability Ratios of Listed Banks in Nigeria?" investigated Olayinka (2017). IFRS had an impact on the profitability ratios of LDMBs in Nigeria, according to secondary data and regression analysis. As a result, the report recommended that banks should embrace and implement IFRS to improve their performance. Ibanichuka (2018) conducted a study in Nigeria utilizing secondary data and a multiple regression technique to examine the adoption of IFRS and the financial performance of petroleum marketing companies. It was discovered that the implementation of IFRS and the financial performance of petroleum marketing organizations in Nigeria had a beneficial link. The study concluded that firms should embrace and use IFRS in order to improve their performance. Yahama (2018) evaluated the implementation of IFRS and the value relevance of accounting information of LDMBs in Nigeria, utilizing secondary data and simple regression analysis. The findings revealed a link between the implementation of IFRS and the value relevance of LDMB accounting information. Similarly, Abba, Alabede, Okwa, and Soje (2018) used the Generalized Least Square technique to examine the impact of IFRS adoption on the overall asset quality of LDMBs in Nigeria from 2006 to 2015. Secondary data were obtained from banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, and it was discovered that the implementation of the IFRS(IFRS) had a considerable impact on the asset quality of Nigerian banks.

Furthermore, Elosiuba and Okoye (2018) used secondary data on eight sampled listed banks in Nigeria to study the impact of IFRS adoption on LDMB performance during 2011 and 2012, reflecting the GAAP and IFRS adoption periods, respectively. The variables employed in the study were profitability, liquidity, loan grants, and market value, and they were analyzed using the One Sample Evaluate of Analyses, while the independent t-statistic was used to test the study's hypotheses. The mean values for profitability, liquidity, and market value were found to be higher in the GAAP era (2011) than in the IFRS era (2012), indicating that IFRS adoption has a negative influence on bank profitability and liquidity, although loan grant was higher in the IFRS period of 2012.

Ekwe, Abaa, Okolor and Ashibeti (2020) carried out a study on the adoption of IFRS and financial performance of LDMBs in Nigeria using *ex-post facto* research design. The study used secondary data through annual reports and accounts of sampled LDMBs. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used as a data analysis tool, and the results revealed that the adoption of IFRS increased the mean value of banks in Nigeria. The implementation of IFRS had no substantial impact on earnings per share, return on asset, or return on equity, according to the study. According to the survey, banks should ensure that their employees are appropriately taught in order to maximize the value of IFRS implementation. According to the study, relevant regulatory agencies should ensure strict adherence.

Based on the literature reviews conducted above, it can be seen that there are mixed findings on the effect of IFRS adoption in Nigerian and abroad because some researchers found a positive and significant effect of IFRS on performance of firms while others found a negative effect of IFRS adoption, consequently, this opens a gap for further studies to be conducted on the impact of IFRS.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study applied *expost-facto* research design on the data extracted from the financial statements of sampled banks in Nigeria. The population of this study was all the fourteen (14) banks that are quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December 2020. The sample size of this study was six (6) banks drawn from the population of 14 banks and it was arrived at using purposive/judgmental sampling method after setting two criteria where all the banks that met them had a chance of being selected. One of the criteria was the requirement that, the bank must be listed on the floor of the NSE as far back as 2004 and the bank must not have changed its original name from 2004-2020.

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The data collected were statistically analyzed using independent T-test of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23 in testing the formulated null hypotheses of the study because it enhances comparability of the differences between two sets of data (Razak, 2000). This justified the use of “pre” and “post” comparative analysis of IFRS 10 adoption on profitability of consolidated financial statements among LDMBs in Nigeria. The scope of the study was 2003-2020 (2003-2011 represented pre-IFRS adoption while 2012-2020 represented post-IFRS adoption and 2012 was considered as the base year of implementation).

Variable Definition and measurement

The variables used to operationalize the constructs are described below.

Table 1. Variables Definition and Measurements

Variables	Definition	Measurements	Source/References
ROA	Return on Assets	Profit after tax/ Total Assets	Ugwudioha (2010) DwiPrastowo (2008)
ROE	Return on Equity	Profit after tax/Total Equity	Ugwudioha (2010) Epstein (2009)
EPS	Earnings Per Share	Profit after tax/ Total Shares issued	Ugwudioha (2010)
DPS	Dividend Per Share	Total dividends paid/ Total Shares issued	Adejoh, & Hasnah, 2014 Ugwudioha (2010)

Source: Compiled by the researcher.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shows the summary descriptive statistics of the independent variables in terms of the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. Under pre IFRS 10 adoption, consolidated Return on Assets (ROA) had a mean of 0.0483 with a standard deviation of 0.0912 respectively. This suggests a low dispersion in Return on Assets of LDMBs in Nigeria pre IFRS 10 adoption. Also, under post IFRS 10 adoption, consolidated Return on Assets had a mean value of 0.0137 with a standard deviation of 0.0366 indicating that there is a wide dispersion of consolidated Return on Assets among Nigerian LDMBs in Nigeria. The negative mean difference of -0.0345 indicates that consolidated Return on Assets of LDMBs in Nigeria was better under pre IFRS 10 adoption.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables

Group Statistics

IFRS 10 ADOPTION		N	Mean	Deviation	Std.	Std.
					Error Mean	
ROA	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	0.01375	0.036588	0.004979	
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	0.04826	0.081907	0.011146	
ROE	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	0.14850	0.176006	0.023951	
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	0.22194	0.239389	0.032577	
EPS	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	1.72000	1.475492	0.200789	
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	1.02687	.830457	0.113011	
DPS	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.75504	.787526	0.107169	
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.52157	.422593	0.057508	

Source: SPSS (23) Output 2022

Considering consolidated Return on Equity (ROE) the table of descriptive statistics shows a mean value of 0.2219 with standard deviation of 0.2394 indicating that there is no wide dispersion in the consolidated Return on Equity of LDMBs in Nigeria under pre IFRS adoption. Furthermore, the mean of 0.1485 and standard deviation of 0.176 indicates that there is no wide deviation among the mean of LDMBs in Nigeria under post IFRS adoption. However, the negative mean difference of -0.0734 indicates that LDMBs in Nigeria earned less return on equity under post IFRS adoption.

Also, consolidated Pre-Earnings Per Share (EPS) had a mean and standard deviation values of 1.0269 and 0.8305 respectively, implying that there is no wide dispersion in consolidated Earnings Per Share of LDMBs in Nigeria under pre IFRS adoption. Under post IFRS, consolidated Earnings Per Share had a mean and standard deviation values of 1.7200 and 1.4755 respectively, implying also, that there is no wide dispersion in consolidated Earnings Per Share of LDMBs in Nigeria. This equally implies that LDMBs in

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Nigeria are similar in terms of generating earning per share. The positive mean balance of 0.6931 indicates that LDMBs in Nigeria had better Earnings Per Share under post IFRS

Furthermore, consolidated Dividend Per Share (DPS) had a mean value of 0.5215 and a standard deviation of 0.4225 showing that there is no wide dispersion between Dividend Per Share of LDMBs in Nigeria pre IFRS adoption. Under post IFRS adoption, consolidated Dividend Per Share had a mean value of 0.7550 and a standard deviation of 0.7875 implying that there is no wide dispersion between consolidated Dividend Per Share of LDMBs in Nigeria. The positive mean balance of 0.2335 indicates that LDMBs in Nigeria did better in terms of consolidated Dividend Per Share under post IFRS

Independent t-test Analysis

This study used four independent variables for determining the impact of IFRS 10 adoption on profitability of consolidated financial statements among LDMBs in Nigeria. The summary of independent t-test results is presented in table 3 below.

Table 3. Independent t-test results

	ROA	ROE	EPS	DPS
Remarks	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean
Post-IFRS Adoption	0.01375	0.1485	1.720	0.7550
Pre-IFRS Adoption	0.0483	0.2219	1.0268	0.5216
Mean difference	-0.0345	-0.0734	0.6931	0.2335
F-Value	10.783	1.155	18.068	21.821
T-Values	-2.827	-1.816	3.008	1.920
Sig. (2-tailed) P-Values	0.006	0.072	0.003	0.058

Source: SPSS (Version 23) Outputs using independent t-test

A formulated null hypothesis that IFRS adoption has no significant impact on consolidated return on assets of LDMBs in Nigeria was tested and the results revealed that IFRS 10 adoption had a negative and significant impact on the consolidated return on assets among LDMBs in Nigeria, because there was a probability value of 0.006% which was less than 0.05% level of significance ($0.006\% < 0.05\%$). This provided evidence to reject the null hypothesis which stated that IFRS 10 adoption has no significant impact on consolidated return on assets among LDMBs in Nigeria. The finding of this study is consistent with those of Elosiuba and Okoye (2018) who stated that IFRS adoption had negative and significant impact on return on assets of firms. It opposes the study of Yahaya, Yusuf and Dania (2015) and Uzodimma and Okpala (2017).

Considering consolidated Return on Equity, Table 3, shows that the probability value of 0.072 is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.072\% > 0.05\%$). On the basis of this, the study therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis which stated that IFRS 10 adoption has no significant impact on consolidated return on equity among LDMBs in Nigeria. This finding is well supported by previous documented study by Ekwe, Abaa, Okrolor and Ashibeti (2020). From Table 3, consolidated Earnings per share had a probability value of 0.003% which is less than 0.05% ($0.003\% < 0.05\%$). On the basis of this, the study rejected the null hypothesis which stated that IFRS 10 adoption has no significant impact on consolidated earnings per share among LDMBs in Nigeria and this position is supported by previous studies Yahaya, Yusuf and Dania (2015) Uzodimma and Okpala (2017) while it opposes the finding of Ekwe, Abaa, Okrolor and Ashibeti (2020).

Table 3, also revealed that consolidated dividend per share had a p-value of 0.058 which is significant because the probability value of 0.058 is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.058 > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that IFRS 10 adoption has no significant impact on consolidated dividend per share of LDMBs in Nigeria failed to be rejected. This finding is not consistent with that of Yahaya, Yusuf and Dania (2015); Uzodimma and Okpala (2017) while it opposes the findings of Ekwe, Abaa, Okrolor and Ashibeti (2020) who found a negative and significant impact.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

IFRS 10 adoption had negative and significant impact on return on assets of LDMBs in Nigeria. This implies that IFRS 10 adoption resulted in lower consolidated return on assets among LDMBs in Nigeria. It was also concluded that IFRS 10 adoption had negative but insignificant impact on the consolidated return on equity among listed deposit banks Nigerian in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study concluded that IFRS 10 adoption had positive and significant impact on consolidated earnings per share among LDMBs in Nigeria because an increased earnings per share was recorded under post IFRS 10.

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Furthermore, IFRS 10 adoption had positive and insignificant impact on dividend per share among LDMBs in Nigeria over the period of the study, because higher dividend per share was recorded under post IFRS 10. Based on the conclusion of the study, it was recommended that shareholders and management of LDMBs in Nigerian should ensure that their boards of directors comply more with IFRS 10 requirements in order to boost the consolidated return on equity, earnings per share and dividend per share among LDMBs in Nigeria.

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Data Set of the Study (Pre-IFRS "1" and Post-IFRS "2" Data)

BANKS	YEARS	ROA	ROE	EPS	DPS	CODE
ACCESS	2003	0.0111	0.024	0.25	0.23	1
	2004	0.0089	0.042	0.14	0.12	1
	2005	0.0311	0.0306	0.13	0	1
	2006	0.0074	0.0356	0.12	0.1	1
	2007	0.0042	0.0255	0.11	0	1
	2008	0.0185	0.2143	0.87	0.4	1
	2009	0.0154	0.0933	1.73	0.4	1
GTB	2010	0.0339	0.1238	1.41	0.7	1
	2011	0.0179	0.0708	0.72	0.2	1
	2003	0.0140	1.0422	1.32	0.73	1

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	2004	0.038	0.191	1.32	0.62	1
	2005	0.0311	0.2603	1.74	0.84	1
	2006	0.0317	0.1592	1.1	0.52	1
	2007	0.0259	0.2169	1.45	0.7	1
	2008	0.0273	0.2325	1.67	1	1
	2009	0.0305	0.1563	1.88	0.75	1
	2010	0.0233	0.1265	1.28	1	1
	2011	0.0342	0.75	1.27	1	1
UBA	2003	0.012	0.032	1.44	0.83	1
	2004	0.0223	0.3154	2.99	0.72	1
	2005	0.0156	0.289	2.23	1.2	1
	2006	0.0186	0.2628	2.49	0.6	1
	2007	0.013	0.2408	1.86	1	1
	2008	0.018	0.1203	2.41	1.2	1
	2009	0.0263	0.2126	3.05	1	1
	2010	0.0095	0.0786	0.6	0.1	1
	2011	0.0092	0.0686	1.6	0.07	1
ZENITH	2003	0.013	0.125	1.54	0.95	1
	2004	0.026	0.2266	1.43	0.84	1
	2005	0.0226	0.1469	0.23	1.32	1
	2006	0.0217	0.1888	1.19	0.7	1
	2007	0.0188	0.1224	0.191	1.1	1
	2008	0.0198	0.1551	1.05	0.85	1
	2009	0.0276	0.1374	2.78	1.7	1
	2010	0.0116	0.5592	0.58	0.45	1
	2011	0.0186	0.095	1.06	0.85	1
FCMB	2003	0.012	0.412	0.46	0.3	1
	2004	0.0186	0.1326	0.3	0.09	1
	2005	0.0108	0.1291	0.43	0.12	1
	2006	0.0155	0.1105	0.25	0.075	1
	2007	0.009	0.1076	0.36	0.1	1
	2008	0.0124	0.1874	0.61	0.3	1
	2009	0.0294	0.1038	1.23	0.5	1
	2010	0.0157	0.056	0.4	0.05	1
	2011	0.0142	0.0569	0.45	0.15	1
ECOBANK	2003	0.3802	0.5433	1.19	0.75	1
	2004	0.2779	0.2759	1.08	0.14	1
	2005	0.3026	0.2774	0.12	0.05	1
	2006	0.2316	0.2299	0.9	0.12	1
	2007	0.2522	0.2312	0.1	0.04	1
	2008	0.0999	1.2754	0.12	0.3	1
	2009	0.0717	0.5808	0.9	0.2	1
	2010	0.1259	0.114	0.12	0.09	1
	2011	-0.0022	-0.0105	-0.8	0	1
ACCESS	2012	0.0179	0.0708	0.72	0.2	2
	2013	0.0148	0.075	0.76	0.2	2
	2014	0.0285	0.1856	1.72	0.25	2

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	2015	0.0203	0.1427	1.59	0.35	2
	2016	0.0201	0.1456	1.75	0.25	2
	2017	0.0244	0.1634	1.67	0.3	2
	2018	0.0206	0.1518	2.21	0.4	2
	2019	0.0293	0.1961	2	0.36	2
	2020	0.0247	0.1822	2.65	0.48	2
GTB	2012	0.0342	0.75	1.24	1.00	2
	2013	0.0314	0.2033	1.63	0.85	2
	2014	0.0493	0.5868	3.06	1.55	2
	2015	0.043	0.6094	3.17	1.7	2
	2016	0.046	0.6681	3.47	1.75	2
	2017	0.0436	0.2442	3.35	1.9	2
	2018	0.0415	0.2188	4.31	2.05	2
	2019	0.0523	0.293	4.02	2.28	2
	2020	0.0498	0.2626	5.17	2.46	2
UBA	2012	0.0092	0.0686	0.6	0.07	2
	2013	0.024	0.2150	1.44	0.12	2
	2014	0.0209	0.179	1.41	0.13	2
	2015	0.017	0.1421	1.22	0.13	2
	2016	0.0214	0.1408	1.36	0.24	2
	2017	-0.0098	-0.096	-0.51	0	2
	2018	0.0187	0.1216	1.31	0.26	2
	2019	-0.0118	-0.1152	-0.61	0	2
	2020	0.0224	0.1459	1.57	0.31	2
ZENITH	2012	0.0186	0.095	1.06	0.85	2
	2013	0.0172	0.1029	1.18	0.95	2
	2014	0.0212	0.2184	3.19	1.6	2
	2015	0.0189	0.1909	3.01	1.75	2
	2016	0.0273	0.1803	2.95	1.75	2
	2017	0.0263	0.1806	3.15	1.85	2
	2018	0.0278	0.1935	3.8	2.25	2
	2019	0.0316	0.2167	3.78	2.222	2
	2020	0.0334	0.2322	4.56	2.7	2
FCMB	2012	0.0142	0.0569	0.45	0.15	2
	2013	-0.023	0.018	-0.7	0	2
	2014	-0.0132	-0.078	0.7	0.3	2
	2015	0.018	0.1052	0.8	0.3	2
	2016	0.0062	0.046	0.27	0.62	2
	2017	0.0022	0.0196	0.13	0.6	2
	2018	0.0028	0.0286	0.19	0.2	2
	2019	0.0026	0.0235	0.16	0.72	2
	2020	0.0034	0.0343	0.23	0.24	2
ECOBANK	2012	-0.0022	-0.0105	-0.8	0	2
	2013	-0.2200	-0.0105	-0.8	0	2
	2014	0.0146	0.1451	2.75	0.45	2
	2015	0.0065	0.076	2.66	0.4	2
	2016	0.0145	0.1443	0.95	0.4	2

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	2017	0.0045	0.045	0.56	0.2	2
	2018	-0.009	-0.1092	2.59	0.2	2
	2019	0.0054	0.054	0.67	0.24	2
	2020	-0.0108	-0.131	3.11	0.24	2

Source: Annual Reports and Accounts of Sampled Banks

Group Statistics

	IFRS 10 ADOPTION	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
ROA	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.01375	.036588	.004979
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.04826	.081907	.011146
ROE	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.14850	.176006	.023951
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.22194	.239389	.032577
EPS	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	1.72000	1.475492	.200789
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	1.02687	.830457	.113011
DPS	POST IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.75504	.787526	.107169
	PRE IFRS 10 ADOPTION	54	.52157	.422593	.057508

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
ROA Equal variances assumed	10.783	.001	-	106	.006	-.034506	.012208	-.058708	-.010303
			2.827						
ROA Equal variances not assumed	10.783	.001	-	73.342	.006	-.034506	.012208	-.058833	-.010178
			2.827						
ROE Equal variances assumed	1.155	.285	-	106	.072	-.073437	.040434	-.153601	.006727
			1.816						
ROE Equal variances not assumed	1.155	.285	-	97.342	.072	-.073437	.040434	-.153684	.006810
			1.816						
EPS Equal variances assumed	18.068	.000	3.008	106	.003	.693130	.230408	.236324	1.149935
			3.008						
EPS Equal variances not assumed	18.068	.000	3.008	83.517	.003	.693130	.230408	.234900	1.151359
			3.008						
DPS Equal variances assumed	21.821	.000	1.920	106	.058	.233463	.121623	-.007667	.474593
			1.920						
DPS Equal variances not assumed	21.821	.000	1.920	81.186	.058	.233463	.121623	-.008521	.475447
			1.920						